
1. Ouvrages

1. Magnetospheres in the Solar System
Space Physics and Aeronomy, Volume 2, Magnetospheres in the Solar System. Romain Maggiolo (Editor), **Nicolas André (Editor)**, Hiroshi Hasegawa (Editor), Daniel T. Welling (Editor), Yongliang Zhang (Editor-in-Chief), Larry J. Paxton (Editor-in-Chief). Geophysical Monograph Series, Vol. 259. ISBN: 978-1-119-50752-9, 800 pp. American Geophysical Union, Wiley, 2021.

2. Chapitres d'ouvrage

1. C.S. Arridge, **André, N.**, Bertucci, C. L., Garnier, P., Jackman, C. M., Németh, Z., Rymer, A. M., Sergis, N., Szego, K., Coates, A. J., Crary, F. J., Upstream of Saturn and Titan, *Space Science Reviews*, 162, 25-83, 2011
2. V. Pierrard, J. Goldstein, **N. André**, V. Jordanova, G. Kotova, J. F. Lemaire, M. Liemohn, and H. Matsui, Physics-based models of the plasmasphere, *Space Science Reviews*, 145, 1-2, 193-229, 2009
3. F. Darrouzet, D. Gallagher, **N. André**, D. L. Carpenter, I. Dandouras, P. Decreau, J. De Keyser, R. Denton, J. Foster, J. Goldstein, M. B. Moldwin, B. W. Reinisch, B. Sandel, and J. Tu, Plasmaspheric Density Structures and Dynamics: Properties observed by the CLUSTER and IMAGE missions, *Space Science Reviews*, Volume 145, Issue 1-2, 55-106, 2009

3. Revues à comité de lecture

Publications soumises

N. André et al., Proserpine, a Mission Concept to Assess the Origin and Habitability of Ceres the Closest Ocean World, *Planetary Science Journal*, 09/2023

Pelcener, S., N. André, et al., Temporal and spatial variability of the electron environment at the orbit of Ganymede as observed by Juno, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics*, 09/2023

Rabia, J., Q. Nénon, N. André et al., Influence of the Jovian current sheet models on the mapping of the UV auroral footprints of Io, Europa, and Ganymede, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics*, 09/2023

Rojo, M. et al., Electron moments derived from the Mercury Electron Analyzer during the cruise phase of BepiColombo, *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 09/2023

Hess, S., L. Leclercq, N. André, B. Cecconi, Monitoring the spacecraft charging effects on science instruments using SPIS connection to SPASE virtual observatory databases, *Astronomy and Computing*, 09/2023

Fraenz, M. et al., Spacecraft outgassing observed by the BepiColombo ion spectrometers, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics*, 09/2023

Kieokaew, R. et al., Physics-based model of solar wind stream interaction regions: Interfacing between Multi-VP and 1D MHD for operational forecasting at L1, *Journal of Space Weather and Space Climate*, 01/2023

Louarn, P. et al., Skewness and Kurtosis of Solar Wind Proton Distribution Functions: the Normal Inverse-Gaussian Model and its Implications, *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 09/2023

Hadid, L. Z., D. Delcourt, Y. Saito, M. Franz, S. Yokota, B. Fiethe, C. Verdeil, B. Katra, F. Leblanc, H. Fischer, M. Persson, S. Aizawa, N. André, A. Fedorov, D. Fontaine, N. Krupp, H. Michalik, J.-M. Illiano, J.-J. Berthelier, H. Kruger, Y. Harada, G. Murakami, and S. Matsuda, BepiColombo observations of escaping carbon and oxygen ions in Venus magnetosheath, *Nature Astronomy*, 2022
Aizawa, S., R. Modolo, N. André, J. M. Raines, Escape of planetary ions from Mercury's magnetosphere under different solar wind conditions, *Geoscience Letters*, 2022

Aizawa, S., A.L.E. Werner, N. André, R. Modolo, S. A. Boardsen, F. Leblanc, V. Genot, J. M. Raines, F. Lavorenti, P. Henri, and F. Califano, Influence of IMF rotation in the solar wind on the response of Mercury's magnetosphere: revisiting Mariner 10 observations, *Planetary Space Science*, 2022

Fung, S., et al., SPASE Metadata as a Heliophysics Science-Enabling Tool, *Advances in Space Research*, 2022

Publications parues

134 publications parues, 11 en 1^{er} auteur, 30 en 2nd ou 3^{ème} auteur, 34 avec étudiants encadrés

2023

(134) Aizawa, S., Y. Harada, N. André, Y. Saito, et al., Direct evidence of substorm-related impulsive injections of electrons at Mercury, *Nature Communications*, Volume 14, article id. 4019, [https://doi.org/ 10.1038/s41467-023-39565-4](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-39565-4)

(133) Rabia, J., V. Hue, J. Szalay, N. André et al., Evidence for electrostatic and Alfvénic accelerations in the Europa footprint tail revealed by Juno in-situ measurements, *Geophysical Research Letters*, Volume 50, Issue 12, article id. e2023GL103131, <https://doi.org/10.1029/2023GL103131>

(132) Lavraud, B., et al., What is the Heliopause? Importance of Magnetic Reconnection and Measurement Requirements, *Frontiers in Astronomy and Space Sciences*, vol. 10, id. 1060618, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fspas.2023.1060618>

(131) Signoles, C. et al., Influence of Solar Wind Variations on the Shapes of Venus' Plasma Boundaries Based on Venus Express Observations, *The Astrophysical Journal*, Volume 954, Issue 1, id.95, 11 pp., <https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ace7b1>

(130) Berthomé, E., P. Devoto, N. André, Design of a fast and low-noise front-end electronics developed for the measurements of low- and medium-energy charged particles

in space plasma environments, *Review of Scientific Instruments*, Volume 94, Issue 7, id.074503, 9 pp., <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0144974>

(129) Moroni, M. et al., Micro-meteoroids impact vaporization as source for Ca and CaO exosphere along Mercury's orbit, *Icarus*, Volume 401, article id. 115616, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.icarus.2023.115616>

(128) Jackson, B. et al., Forecasting Heliospheric CME Solar-Wind Parameters Using the UCSD Time-Dependent Tomography and ISEE Interplanetary Scintillation Data: The 10 March 2022 CME, *Solar Physics*, Volume 298, Issue 5, article id.74, <https://10.1007/s11207-023-02169-8>

2022

(127) Persson, A., S. Aizawa, N. André, S. Barabash, S. Saito, Y. Harada, S. Heyner, S. Orsini, A. Fedorov, C. Mazelle, Y. Futaana, L. Z. Hadid, M. Volwerk, G. Collinson, B. Sanchez-Cano, A. Barthe, E. Penou, S. Yokota, V. Genot, J. A. Sauvaud, D. Delcourt, M. Fraenz, R. Modolo, A. Milillo, H.-U. Auster, I. Richter, J. Z. D. Mieth, P. Louarn, C. J. Owen, T. S. Horbury, K. Asamura, S. Matsuda, H. Nilsson, M. Wieser, T. Alberti, A. Varsani, V. Mangano, A. Mura, L. Gunter, G. Laky, H. Jeszenszky, K. Masunaga, C. Signoles, M. Rojo, and G. Murakami, Persson, M., Aizawa, S., André, N. et al. BepiColombo mission confirms stagnation region of Venus and reveals its large extent. *Nat Commun* 13, 7743 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-35061-3>

(126) Wimmer-Schweingruber, R.F., N. André, S. Barabash et al., STELLA—Potential European contributions to a NASA-led interstellar probe, *Frontiers in Astronomy and Space Sciences*, vol. 9, id. 1063849, doi:[10.3389/fspas.2022.1063849](https://doi.org/10.3389/fspas.2022.1063849)

(125) Al Saati, S. et al., Magnetosphere-Ionosphere-Thermosphere Coupling Study at Jupiter Based on Juno's First 30 Orbits and Modeling Tools, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics*, Volume 127, Issue 10, article id. e2022JA030586, doi: [10.1029/2022JA030586](https://doi.org/10.1029/2022JA030586)

(124) Futaana, Y., et al., Galactic Cosmic Rays at Mars and Venus: Temporal Variations from Hours to Decades Measured as the Background Signal of Onboard Microchannel Plates, *The Astrophysical Journal*, Volume 940, Issue 2, id.178, 12 pp., doi:[10.3847/1538-4357/ac9a49](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ac9a49)

(123) Deniau, A., Q. Nénon, N. André, et al., MAVEN Proton Observations Near the Martian Moon Phobos: Does Phobos Backscatter Solar Wind Protons?, *Geophysical Research Letters*, Volume 49, Issue 23, article id. e2022GL101014, doi: [10.1029/2022GL101014](https://doi.org/10.1029/2022GL101014)

(122) Mousis, O., A. Bouquet, Y. Langevin, N. André et al., Moonraker: Enceladus Multiple Flyby Mission, *The Planetary Science Journal*, Volume 3, Issue 12, id.268, 12 pp., doi:[10.3847/PSJ/ac9c03](https://doi.org/10.3847/PSJ/ac9c03)

(121) Harada, Y., S. Aizawa, Y. Saito, N. André, et al., BepiColombo Mio Observations of Low-Energy Ions During the First Mercury Flyby: Initial Results, *Geophysical Research Letters*, Volume 49, Issue 17, article id. e00279, doi:[10.1029/2022GL100279](https://doi.org/10.1029/2022GL100279)

(120) Lavorenti, L, P. Henri, F. Califano, J. Deca, S. Aizawa, N. André, J. Benkhoff, Electron dynamics in small magnetospheres. Insights from global, fully kinetic plasma simulations of the planet Mercury, *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, Volume 664, id.A133, 11 pp., doi://[10.1051/0004-6361/202243911](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/202243911), 2022

(119) Aizawa, S., M. Persson, T. Menez, N. André et al., LatHyS global hybrid simulation of the BepiColombo second Venus flyby, *Planetary and Space Sciences*, 218, doi: [10.1016/j.pss.2022.105499](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pss.2022.105499), 2022

(118) Sun, W. et al., Dayside magnetopause reconnection and flux transfer events under radial interplanetary magnetic field (IMF): BepiColombo Earth-flyby observations, *Annales Geophysicae*, 40, doi:[10.5194/angeo-40-217-2022](https://doi.org/10.5194/angeo-40-217-2022), 2022

2021

(117) Fedorov, A. et al., Switchback-like structures observed by Solar Orbiter, *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 656, doi:[10.1051/0004-6361/202141246](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/202141246), 2021

(116) Lavraud, B. et al., Magnetic reconnection as a mechanism to produce multiple thermal proton populations and beams locally in the solar wind, *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 656, doi:[10.1051/0004-6361/202141149](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/202141149), 2021

(115) Louarn, P. et al., Multiscale views of an Alfvénic slow solar wind: 3D velocity distribution functions observed by the Proton-Alpha Sensor of Solar Orbiter, *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 656, doi:[10.1051/0004-6361/202141095](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/202141095), 2021

(114) D'Amicis, R. et al., First Solar Orbiter observation of the Alfvénic slow wind and identification of its solar source, *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 656, doi:[10.1051/0004-6361/202140938](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/202140938), 2021

(113) Steinvall, K. et al., Solar wind current sheets and deHoffmann-Teller analysis. First results from Solar Orbiter's DC electric field measurements, *Astronomy @ Astrophysics*, 656, doi:[10.1051/0004-6361/202140855](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/202140855), 2021

(112) Roussos, E. et al., The in-situ exploration of Jupiter's radiation belts, *Experimental Astronomy*, doi:[10.1007/s10686-021-09801-0](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10686-021-09801-0), 2021

(111) Wang, Y. et al., A Preliminary Study of Magnetosphere-Ionosphere-Thermosphere Coupling at Jupiter: Juno Multi-Instrument Measurements and Modeling Tools, *Journal of Geophysical Research (Space Physics)*, 126, doi:[10.1029/2021JA029469](https://doi.org/10.1029/2021JA029469), 2021

(110) Hadid, L.Z. et al., BepiColombo's cruise phase: unique opportunity for synergistic observations, *Frontiers in Astronomy and Space Science*, 8, doi:[10.3389/fspas.2021.71802](https://doi.org/10.3389/fspas.2021.71802), 2021

(109) Volwerk, M. et al., Venus's induced magnetosphere during active solar wind conditions at BepiColombo's Venus 1 flyby, *Annales Geophysicae*, 39, doi:[10.5194/angeo-39-811-2021](https://doi.org/10.5194/angeo-39-811-2021), 2021

(108) Saito, Y. et al., Pre-flight Calibration and Near-Earth Commissioning Results of the Mercury Plasma Particle Experiment (MPPE) Onboard MMO (Mio), *Space Science Reviews*, 217, doi:10.1007/s11214-021-00839-2, 2021

(107) Goetz, C. et al., Cometary plasma science, *Experimental Astronomy*, doi:10.1007/s10686-021-09783-z, 2021

(106) Lavorenti, F., et al., Electron acceleration driven by the lower-hybrid-drift instability. An extended quasilinear model, *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 652, doi:10.1051/0004-6361/202141049, 2021

(105) Génot, V. et al., Automated Multi-Dataset Analysis (AMDA): An on-line database and analysis tool for heliospheric and planetary plasma data, *Planetary and Space Sciences*, 201, doi:10.1016/j.pss.2021.105214, 2021

(104) Fletcher, L. et al., Ice giant system exploration within ESA's Voyage 2050, *Experimental Astronomy*, doi:10.1007/s10686-021-09759-z, 2021

(103) Maggiolo, R. et al., Magnetospheres in the Solar System, doi: 10.1002/9781119815624, 2021

(102) Blanc, M. et al., Science Goals and Mission Objectives for the Future Exploration of Ice Giants Systems: A Horizon 2061 Perspective, *Space Science Reviews*, 217, doi: 10.1007/s11214-020-00769-5, 2021

(101) Aizawa, S. et al., Cross-comparison of global simulation models applied to Mercury's dayside magnetosphere, *Planetary and Space Sciences*, 198, doi:10.1016/j.pss.2021.105176, 2021

2020

(100) Blanc, M. et al., Joint Europa Mission (JEM): a multi-scale study of Europa to characterize its habitability and search for extant life, *Planetary and Space Sciences*, 193, doi: 10.1016/j.pss.2020.104960, 2020

(99) Aizawa, S. et al., Statistical study of non-adiabatic energization and transport in Kelvin-Helmholtz vortices at Mercury, *Planetary and Space Sciences*, 193, doi: 10.1016/j.pss.2020.105079, 2020

(98) Fletcher, L. et al., Ice Giant Systems: The scientific potential of orbital missions to Uranus and Neptune, *Planetary and Space Sciences*, 191, doi: 10.1016/j.pss.2020.105030, 2020

(97) Aizawa, S. et al., MESSENGER Observations of Planetary Ion Characteristics in the Vicinity of Kelvin-Helmholtz Vortices at Mercury, *Journal of Geophysical Research (Space Physics)*, 125, doi: 10.1029/2020JA027871, 2020

(96) Owen, C.J. et al., The Solar Orbiter Solar Wind Analyser (SWA) suite, *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 642, doi:10.1051/0004-6361/201937259, 2020

(95) Milillo, A., et al., Investigating Mercury's Environment with the Two-Spacecraft BepiColombo Mission, *Space Science Reviews*, 216, doi: 10.1007/s11214-020-00712-8, 2020

(94) Kasaba, K. et al., Mission Data Processor Aboard the BepiColombo Mio Spacecraft: Design and Scientific Operation Concept, *Space Science Reviews*, 216, doi:[10.1007/s11214-020-00658-x](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11214-020-00658-x), 2020

(93) Erard, S. et al., Virtual European Solar and Planetary Access: a Planetary Science Virtual Observatory cornerstone, *Data Science Journal*, 19, doi: 10.5334/dsj-2020-022, 2020

(92) Cecconi, B. et al., MASER: A Science Ready Toolbox for Low Frequency Radio Astronomy, *Data Science Journal*, 19, doi:10.5334/dsj-2020-012, 2020

2019

(91) Chassela, O. et al., Thermal characterization of resistance and gain of microchannel plate (MCP) detectors for the JENI experiment, *CEAS Space Journal*, Volume 11, Issue 4, pp.597-605, 2019

(90) **André, N.**, et al., Detection efficiency of microchannel plates to penetrating radiation in space, *CEAS Space Journal*, Volume 11, Issue 4, 2019

(89) Holmberg, M.K.G., **N. André** et al., MAVEN and MEX Multi-instrument Study of the Dayside of the Martian Induced Magnetospheric Structure Revealed by Pressure Analyses, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics*, Volume 124, Issue 11, pp. 8564-8589, 2019

(88) Brelly, P.L., A. Marchaudon, M. Indurain, O. Witasse, J. Amaya, B. Chide, **N. André**, V. Génot, A. Goutenoir, M. Bouchemit, Transplanet: A web service dedicated to modeling of planetary ionospheres, *Planetary and Space Science*, Volume 169, p. 35-44, doi :[10.1016/j.pss.2019.02.008](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pss.2019.02.008), 2019

(87) Achilleos, N., P. Guio, **N. André**, A. M. Sorba, A magnetodisc model service for planetary space weather studies, *Journal of Space Weather and Space Climate*, Volume 9, id.A24, doi :[10.1051/swsc/2019022](https://doi.org/10.1051/swsc/2019022), 2019

(86) Q. Nénon and **N. André**, Evidence of Europa Neutral Gas Torii from Energetic Sulfur Ion Measurements, *Geophysical Research Letters*, Volume 46, Issue 7, pp. 3599-3606, doi : [10.1029/2019GL082200](https://doi.org/10.1029/2019GL082200), 2019

2018

(85) Jakosky, B. et al., Loss of the Martian atmosphere to space: Present-day loss rates determined from MAVEN observations and integrated loss through time, *Icarus*, Volume 315, p. 146-157, doi :[10.1016/j.icarus.2018.05.030](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.icarus.2018.05.030), 2018

(84) Snodgrass, C., et al., The Castalia mission to Main Belt Comet 133P/Elst-Pizarro, *Advances in Space Research*, Volume 62, Issue 8, p. 1947-1976, doi : [10.1016/j.asr.2017.09.011](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asr.2017.09.011), 2018

(83) Louarn, P., et al., Observation of Electron Conics by Juno: Implications for Radio Generation and Acceleration Processes, *Geophysical Research Letters*, Volume 45, Issue 18, , doi : [10.1029/2018GL078973](https://doi.org/10.1029/2018GL078973), 2018

(82) Futaana, Y. et al., SELMA mission: How do airless bodies interact with space environment? The Moon as an accessible laboratory, *Planetary and Space Science*, Volume 156, p. 23-40, doi:[10.1016/j.pss.2017.11.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pss.2017.11.002), 2018

(81) Génot, V. et al., Science data visualization in planetary and heliospheric contexts with 3DView, *Planetary and Space Science*, Volume 150, p. 111-130, doi : [10.1016/j.pss.2017.07.007](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pss.2017.07.007), 2018

(80) Génot, V. et al., TREPS, a tool for coordinate and time transformations in space physics, *Planetary and Space Science*, Volume 150, 2018

(79) Erard, S. et al., VESPA: A community-driven Virtual Observatory in Planetary Science, *Planetary and Space Science*, Volume 150, p. 65-85, doi:[10.1016/j.pss.2017.05.013](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pss.2017.05.013), 2018

(78) **André, N.** et al., Virtual Planetary Space Weather Services offered by the Europlanet H2020 Research Infrastructure, *Planetary and Space Science*, Volume 150, p. 50-59, doi:[10.1016/j.pss.2017.04.020](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pss.2017.04.020), 2018

(77) Modolo, R., et al., The LatHyS database for planetary plasma environment investigations: Overview and a case study of data/model comparisons, *Planetary and Space Science*, Volume 150, p. 13-21, doi: [10.1016/j.pss.2017.02.015](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pss.2017.02.015), 2018

(76) Holmberg, M.K.G., et al., Density Structures, Dynamics, and Seasonal and Solar Cycle Modulations of Saturn's Inner Plasma Disk, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics*, Volume 122, Issue 12, pp. 12,258-12,273, doi : [10.1002/2017JA024311](https://doi.org/10.1002/2017JA024311), 2018

2017

(75) Rouillard, A. et al., A propagation tool to connect remote-sensing observations with in-situ measurements of heliospheric structures, *Planetary and Space Science*, Volume 147, doi:[10.1016/j.pss.2017.07.001](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pss.2017.07.001), 2017

(74) Louarn, P. et al., Generation of the Jovian hectometric radiation: First lessons from Juno, *Geophysical Research Letters*, Volume 44, Issue 10, pp. 4439-4446, doi: [10.1002/2017GL072923](https://doi.org/10.1002/2017GL072923), 2017

(73) Tao, C., L. Lamy, R. Prangée, **N. André**, S.V. Badman, Auroral electron energy estimation using the H/H₂ brightness ratio applied to Jupiter, *Planetary Radio Emissions VIII, Proceedings of the 8th International Workshop held at Seggau, Austria, October 25-27, 2016*. Edited by G. Fischer, G. Mann, M. Panchenko, and P. Zarka. Austrian Academy of Sciences Press, Vienna, 2017, p. 139-149, doi : [10.1553/PRE8s139](https://doi.org/10.1553/PRE8s139), 2017

(72) Steckiewicz, M. et al., Comparative study of the Martian suprathermal electron depletions based on Mars Global Surveyor, Mars Express, and Mars Atmosphere and Volatile Evolution mission

observations, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics*, Volume 122, Issue 1, pp. 857-873, doi: [10.1002/2016JA023205](https://doi.org/10.1002/2016JA023205), 2017

2016

(71) Tao, C. et al., Variation of Jupiter's aurora observed by Hisaki/EXCEED: 2. Estimations of auroral parameters and magnetospheric dynamics, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics*, Volume 121, Issue 5, pp. 4055-4071, doi:[10.1002/2015JA021272](https://doi.org/10.1002/2015JA021272), 2016

(70) Tao, C. et al., Variation of Jupiter's aurora observed by Hisaki/EXCEED: 1. Observed characteristics of the auroral electron energies compared with observations performed using HST/STIS, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics*, Volume 121, Issue 5, pp. 4041-4054, doi:[10.1002/2015JA021271](https://doi.org/10.1002/2015JA021271), 2016

(69) Arridge, C.S., et al., Cassini in situ observations of long-duration magnetic reconnection in Saturn's magnetotail, *Nature Physics*, Volume 12, Issue 3, pp. 268-271, 2016

2015

(68) Steckiewicz, M. et al., Altitude dependence of nightside Martian suprathermal electron depletions as revealed by MAVEN observations, *Geophysical Research Letters*, Volume 42, Issue 21, pp. 8877-8884, doi:[10.1002/2015GL065257](https://doi.org/10.1002/2015GL065257), 2015

(67) Schippers, P. et al., Nanodust Detection between 1 and 5 AU Using Cassini Wave Measurements, *The Astrophysical Journal*, Volume 806, Issue 1, article id. 77, 7 pp., 2015

2014

(66) Mousis, O. et al., Scientific rationale for Saturn's in situ exploration, *Planetary and Space Science*, Volume 104, p. 29-47, 2014

(65) Achilleos, N., N. André, X. Blanco-Cano, P.C. Brandt, P.A. Delamere, and R.M. Winglee, The interchange instability, *Space Science Reviews*, Online First, 2014

(64) Louarn, P., N. André, C.M. Jackman, S. Kasahara, E.A. Kronberg, and M. Vogt, Magnetic reconnection and associated transient phenomena within the magnetospheres of Jupiter and Saturn, *Space Science Reviews*, Online First, 2014

(63) Jackman, C. M., Arridge, C. S., André, N., Bagenal, F., Birn, J., Freeman, M. P., Jia, X., Kidder, A., Milan, S. E., Radioti, A., Slavin, J. A., Vogt, M. F., Volwerk, M., Walsh, A. P., Large-Scale Structure and Dynamics of the Magnetotails of Mercury, Earth, Jupiter and Saturn, *Space Science Reviews*, Volume 182, Issue 1-4, pp. 85-154, 2014

(62) Génot, V., N. André, B. Cecconi, M. Bouchemit, E. Budnik, N. Bourrel, M. Gangloff, N. Dufourg, S. Hess, R. Modolo, B. Renard, N. Lormant, L. Beigbeder, D. Popescu, J.-P. Toniutti, Joining the yellow hub: implementations of the Simple Application Messaging Protocol in Space Physics analysis tools, *Astronomy and Computing*, 2014

(61) Erard S., P. Le Sidaner, B. Cecconi, J. Berthier, F. Henry, N. André, V. Génot, C. Jacquey, M. Gangloff, N. Bourrel, B. Schmitt, Planetary Science Virtual Observatory architecture, *Astronomy & Computing*, 2014

(60) Erard S., P. Le Sidaner, B. Cecconi, J. Berthier, F. Henry, M. Molinaro, M. Giardino, N. Bourrel, N. André, M. Gangloff, C. Jacquey, F. Topf, The EPN-TAP protocol for the Planetary Science Virtual Observatory, *Astronomy & Computing*, 2014

(59) Arridge, C.S., N. Achilleos, J. Agarwal, C.B. Agnor, R. Ambrosi, N. André, S.V. Badman, K. Baines, D. Banfield, M. Barthélémy, M. Bisi, J. Blum, T. Bocanegra-Bahamon, B. Bonfond, C. Bracken, P. Brandt, C. Briand, C. Briois, S. Brooks, J. Castillo-Rogez, T. Cavalié, et al., The science case for an orbital mission to Uranus: Exploring the origins and evolution of ice giant planets, *Planetary and Space Sciences*, *Planetary and Space Science*, Volume 104, p. 122-140, 2014

(58) Masters, A., N. Achilleos, C.B. Agnor, S. Campagnola, S. Charnoz, B. Christophe, A.J. Coates, L.N. Fletcher, G.H. Jones, L. Lamy, F. Marzari, N. Nettelmann, J. Ruiz, R. Ambrosi, N. André, A. Bhardwaj, J.J. Fortney, C.J. Hansen, R. Helled, G. Moragas-Klostermeyer, G. Orton, et al., Neptune and Triton: Essential pieces of the Solar System puzzle, *Planetary and Space Science*, Volume 104, p. 108-121, 2014

(57) Collinson, G.A., A. Fedorov, Y. Futaana, K. Masunaga, R. Hartle, G. Stenberg, J. Grebowsky, M. Holstrom, N. André, S. Barabash, and T. Zhang, The extension of ionospheric holes in the ionosphere of Venus, *Journal of Geophysical Research*, 2014

2013

(56) Volwerk, M., **André, N.**, Arridge, C.S., Jackman, C.M., Jia, X., Milan, S.E., Radioti, A., Vogt, M.F., Walsh, A.P., Nakamura, R., Masters, A., Forsyth, C., Comparative magnetotail flapping: an overview of selected events at Earth, Jupiter and Saturn, *Annales Geophysicae*, 31, 817, 2013

(55) Sittler, E., Cooper, J. F., Hartle, R. E., Paterson, W. R., Christian, E. R., Lipatov, A. S., Mahaffy, P. R., Paschalidis, N., Coplan, M. A., Cassidy, T. A., Richardson, J. D., Fegley, B., **André, N.**, Plasma Ion Composition Measurements for Europa, *Planetary Space Sciences*, doi:10.1016/j.pss.2013.01.013, 2013

(54) Allioux, R., Louarn, P., **André, N.**, Model of energetic populations at Ganymede, implications for an orbiter, *Advances in Space Research*, 51, 1204-1212, 2013

2012

(53) Schippers, P., **André, N.**, Gurnett, D.A., Lewis, G.R., Persoon, A.M., Coates, A.J., Identification of field-aligned current systems in Saturn's magnetosphere, *Journal of Geophysical Research*, 117, 10.1029/2011JA017352, 2012

(52) Lamy, L., Prangé, R., Hansen, K. C., Clarke, J. T., Zarka, P., Cecconi, B., Abouadarham, J., **André, N.**, Branduardi-Raymont, G., Gladstone, R., Barthélémy, M., Achilleos, N., Guio, P.,

Dougherty, M. K., Melin, H., Cowley, S. W. H., Stallard, T. S., Nichols, J. D., Ballester, G., Eath-based detection of Uranus' aurorae, *Geophysical Research Letters*, 10.1029/2012GL051312, 2012

(51) Arridge, C.S., **André, N.**, Khurana, K. K., Russell, C. T., Cowley, S. W. H., Provan, G., Andrews, D. J., Jackman, C. M., Coates, A. J., Sittler, E. C., Periodic motion of Saturn's nightside plasma sheet, *Journal of Geophysical Research*, 116, A11205, 2012

(50) Arridge, C.S., Agnor, C. B., **André, N.**, Baines, K. H., Fletcher, L. N., Gautier, D., Hofstadter, M. D., Jones, G. H., Lamy, L., Langevin, Y., Mousis, O., Nettelmann, N., Russell, C. T., Stallard, T., Tiscareno, M. S., Tobie, G., Bacon, A., Chaloner, C., Guest, M., Kemble, S., Peacocke, L., Achilleos, N., Andert, T. P., Banfield, D., Barabash, S., Barthelemy, M., Bertucci, C., Brandt, P., Cecconi, B., Chakrabarti, S., Cheng, A. F., Christensen, U., Christou, A., Coates, A. J., Collinson, G., Cooper, J. F., Courtin, R., Dougherty, M. K., Ebert, R. W., Entradas, M., Fazakerley, A. N., Fortney, J. J., Galand, M., Gustin, J., Hedman, M., Helled, R., Henri, P., Hess, S., Holme, Richard, Karatekin, Ö., Krupp, N., Leisner, J., Martin-Torres, J., Masters, A., Melin, H., Miller, S., Müller-Wodarg, I., Noyelles, B., Paranicas, C., de Pater, I., Pätzold, M., Prangé, R., Quémerais, E., Roussos, E., Rymer, A. M., Sánchez-Lavega, A., Saur, J., Sayanagi, K. M., Schenk, P., Schubert, G., Sergis, N., Sohl, F., Sittler, E. C., Teanby, N. A., Tellmann, S., Turtle, E. P., Vinatier, S., Wahlund, J.-E., Zarka, P., Uranus Pathfinder : eploring the origins and evolution of Ice Giant Planets, *Experimental Astronomy*, 33, 753-791, 2012

2011

(49) Christophe, B., Spilker, L. J., Anderson, J. D., **André, N.**, Asmar, S. W., Aurnou, J., Banfield, D., Barucci, A., Bertolami, O., Bingham, R., Brown, P., Cecconi, B., Courty, J.-M., Dittus, H., Fletcher, L. N., Foulon, B., Francisco, F., Gil, P. J. S., Glassmeier, K. H., Grundy, W., Hansen, C., Helbert, J., Helled, R., Hussmann, H., Lamine, B., Lämmerzahl, C., Lamy, L., Lehoucq, R., Lenoir, B., Levy, A., Orton, G., Páramos, J., Poncy, J., Postberg, F., Progrebekko, S. V., Reh, K. R., Reynaud, S., Robert, C., Samain, E., Saur, J., Sayanagi, K. M., Schmitz, N., Selig, H., Sohl, F., Spilker, T. R., Srama, R., Stephan, K., Touboul, P., Wolf, P., OSS (Outer Solar System) : a fundamental and planetary physics mission to Neptune, Triton and the Kuiper Belt, *Experimental Astronomy*, 34, 203-242, 2012

(48) Arridge, C.S., **André, N.**, McAndrews, H., Bunce, E., Burger, M., Hansen, K.C., Hsu, H.-W., Johnson, R.E., Jones, G.H., Kempf, S., Khurana, K.K., Krupp, N., Kurth, W.S., Leisner, J.S., Paranicas, C., Roussos, E., Russell, C.T., Schippers, P., Sittler, E.C., Smith, H.T., Thomsen, M.F., Dougherty, M.K., Mapping magnetospheric equatorial regions at Saturn from Cassini Prime Mission Observations, *Space Science Reviews*, 164, 1-83, 2011

(47) Kurth, W.S., D.A. Gurnett, J.D. Menietti, R.L. Mutel, M.G. Kivelson, E.J. Bunce, S.W.H. Cowley, D.L. Talboys, M.K. Dougherty, C. Arridge, A. Coates, S. Grimald, L. Lamy, P. Zarka, B. Cecconi, P. Schippers, **N. André**, P. Louarn, D. Mitchell, J.S. Leisner, and M. Morooka, A close encounter with a SKR source region, *Planetary Radio Emissions*, 2011

(46) Schippers, P., C. S. Arridge, J. D. Menietti, D. A. Gurnett, L. Lamy, B. Cecconi, D. G. Mitchell, **N. André**, W. S. Kurth, S. Grimald, M. K. Dougherty, A. J. Coates, N. Krupp, and D. T. Young, Auroral electron distributions within and close to the Saturn Kilometric Radiation source region, *J. Geophys. Res.*, doi:10.1029/2011JA016461, 2011

(45) Arridge, C.S., **André, N.**, Bertucci, C. L., Garnier, P., Jackman, C. M., Németh, Z., Rymer, A. M., Sergis, N., Szego, K., Coates, A. J., Crary, F. J., Upstream of Saturn and Titan, *Space Science Reviews*, 162, 25-83, 2011

2010

(44) Lamy, L., Schippers, P., Zarka, P., Cecconi, B., Arridge, C. S., Dougherty, M. K., Louarn, P., **André, N.**, Kurth, W. S., Mutel, R. L., and 2 coauthors, Properties of Saturn kilometric radiation measured within its source region, *Geophysical Research Letters*, Volume 37, Issue 12, CiteID L12104, 2010

(43) Kopf, A.J., Gurnett, D. A., Menietti, J. D., Schippers, P., Arridge, C. S., Hospodarsky, G. B., Kurth, W. S., Grimald, S., **André, N.**, Coates, A. J., Dougherty, M. K., Electron beams as the source

2009

(42) Génot, V., C. Jacquy, M. Bouchemit, M. Gangloff, A. Fedorov, B. Lavraud, **N. André**, L. Broussillou, C. Harvey, E. Pallier, E. Penou, E. Budnik, R. Hitier, B. Cecconi, D. Heulet, J.-L. Pinçon, Space Weather applications with CDPP/AMDA, *Advances in Space Research*, 2009

(41) G. Lewis, D. Linder, L. Gilbert, D. Kataria, A. Coates, C. arridge, **N. André**, A. Rymer, G. Jones, A. Persoon, D. Gurnett, N. Krupp, D. Young, S. Krimigis, In flight calibration of the Cassini-Huygens CAPS Electron Spectrometer, *Planetary and Space Science*, 2009

(40) P. Schippers, **N. André**, M. Blanc, I. Dandouras, R. E. Johnson, A. J. Coates, and D. T. Young, Identification of Photoelectrons Energy Peaks in Saturn's Inner Neutral Torus, in press in *Journal of Geophysical Research*, 2009

(39) **N. André**, B. Foing, C. Cockell, Special issue with papers from the ESLAB 2008 Symposium on 'Cosmic Cataclysms and Life', *International Journal of Astrobiology*, Volume 8, Issue 3, p. 145-146, 2009

(38) A. Rymer, B. Mauk, T. Hill, **N. André**, D.G. Mitchell, C. Paranicas, D.T. Young, H.T. Smith, A.M. Persoon, J.D. Menietti, G.B. Hospodarsky, A.J. Coates, M.K. Dougherty, Cassini evidence for rapid interchange transport at Saturn, in press in *Planetary and Space Science*, 2009

(37) M. Blanc, M. Fujimoto, R. Pappalardo, S. Sasaki, L. Zelenyi, Y. Alibert, **N. André**, S. Atreya, R. Beebe, W. Benz, A. Coradini, A. Coustenis, V. Dehant, M. Dougherty, P. Drossart, O. Grasset, L. Gurvits, P. Hartogh, H. Hussmann, Y. Kasaba, M. Kivelson, K. Khurana, N. Krupp, P. Louarn, J. Lunine, M. McGrath, D. Mimoun, O. Moussis, J. Oberst, T. Okada, O. Prieto-Ballesteros, D. Prieur, P. Regnier, M. Roos-Serote, J. Schubert, C. Sotin, T. Spilker, Y. Takahaschi, T. Takashima, F. Tosi, D. Turini, and T. Van Hoolst, LAPLACE, a mission to Europa and the Jupiter System for ESA's Cosmic Vision Programme, *Experimental Astronomy*, Volume 23, Issue 3, 849-892, 2009

(36) C. Jacquy, V. Génot, E. Budnik, R. Hitier, M. Bouchemit, M. Gangloff, A. Fedorov, B. Cecconi, **N. André**, B. Lavraud, C. Harvey, F. Deriot, D. Heulet, E. Pallier, E. Penou, and J.-L. Pinc con, AMDA, Automated Multi-Dataset Analysis : A web-based service provided by the CDPP, *Astrophysics and Space Science Proceedings*, 2009

(35) F. Darrouzet, D. Gallagher, **N. André**, D. L. Carpenter, I. Dandouras, P. Decreau, J. De Keyser, R. Denton, J. Foster, J. Goldstein, M. B. Mldwin, B. W. Reinisch, B. Sandel, and J. Tu, Plasmaspheric Density Structures and Dynamics: Properties observed by the CLUSTER and IMAGE missions, *Space Science Reviews*, Volume 145, Issue 1-2, 55-106, 2009

(34) V. Pierrard, J. Goldstein, **N. André**, V. Jordanova, G. Kotova, J. F. Lemaire, M. Liemohn, and H. Matsui, Physics-based models of the plasmasphere, *Space Science Reviews*, 145, 1-2, 193-229, 2009

2008

(33) **N. André**, M. Blanc, S. Maurice, P. Schippers, E. Pallier, T. Gombosi, K. Hansen, D. Young, F. Crary, S. Bolton, E. Sittler, H. Smith, R. Johnson, R. Baragiola, A. Rymer, A. Coates, M. Dougherty, W. Kurth, D. Gurnett, S. Krimigis, D. Mitchell, N. Krupp, D. Hamilton, I. Dandouras, R. Srama, S. Kempf, H. Waite, L. Esposito, J. Clarke, Identification of Saturn's magnetospheric regions and associated plasma processes: Synopsis of Cassini observations during Orbit Insertion, *Reviews of Geophysics*, 46, Issue 4, RG4008, 2008

(32) **N. André** and K. M. Ferrière, Stratification-driven instabilities in a kinetic Io plasma torus with bi-kappa distribution functions, *Journal of Geophysical Research*, 113, doi:10.1029/2008JA013179, 2008

(31) J. L. Burch, J. Goldstein, P. Mokashi, W. S. Lewis, C. Paty, D. T. Young, A. J. Coates, M. K. Dougherty, and **N. André**, On the cause of Saturn's plasma periodicity, *Geophysical Research Letters* (**2.959**), 35, L14105, doi:10.1029/2008GL034951, 2008

(30) P. Schippers, M. Blanc, **N. André**, I. Dandouras, L. Gilbert, G. Lewis, N. Krupp, M. Thomsen, A. Coates, S. Krimigis, D. Young, and M. Dougherty, Multi-instrument analysis of electrons in Saturn's magnetosphere, *Journal of Geophysical Research* (**3.147**), 113, doi:10.1029/2008JA013098, 2008

(29) C. Arridge, **N. André**, K. Khurana, C. Bertucci, L. Gilbert, G. Lewis, A. Coates, and M. Dougherty, Thermal electron periodicities at 20 R_S in Saturn's magnetosphere, *Geophysical Research Letters*, 35, 15107, doi:10.1029/2008GL034132, 2008

(28) G. R. Lewis, **N. André**, C. S. Arridge, A. J. Coates, L. K. Gilbert, D. R. Linder, and A. M. Rymer, Derivation of density and temperature from the Cassini-Huygens CAPS Electron Spectrometer, *Planetary and Space Science*, 56, 901-912, 2008

(27) E. C. Sittler, **N. André**, M. Blanc, M. Burger, R. E. Johnson, A. Coates, A. Rymer, D. Reisenfeld, M. F. Thomsen, A. Persoon, M. Dougherty, H. Smith, R. Baragiola, R. E. Hartle, D. Chornay, M. D. Shappirio, D. Simpson, D. McComas, and D. T. Young, Ion and neutral sources and sinks within Saturn's inner magnetosphere: Cassini result, *Planetary and Space Science*, 54, 1, doi:10.1016/j.pss.2007.06.006, 2008

2007

(26) P. Louarn, W. Kurth, D. Gurnett, G. Hospodarski, A. Persoon, B. Cecconi, A. Lecacheux, P. Zarka, P. Canu, A. Roux, H. Rucker, W. Farrel, M. Kaiser, **N. André**, C. Harvey, M. Blanc, Observations of similar radio signatures at Saturn and Jupiter: implications for the magnetospheric dynamics, *Geophysical Research Letters*, 34, L24S07, doi:10.1029/2007GL030368, 2007

(25) **N. André** and K. M. Ferrière, Comments on Vasyliunas' and Pontius' Studies of the effects of the planetary ionosphere and of the Coriolis force on the interchange instability, *Journal of Geophysical Research*, 112, A10203, doi:10.1029/2006JA011732, 2007

(24) J. L. Burch, J. Goldstein, W. S. Lewis, D. T. Young, A. J. Coates, M. K. Dougherty, and **N. André**, Tethys and Dione: Sources of outward flowing plasma in Saturn's magnetosphere, *Nature*, 447, 7146, doi:10.1038/nature05906, 2007

(23) **N. André**, A. Persoon, J. Goldstein, J. Burch, G. Lewis, A. Coates, A. Rymer, E. Sittler, M. Thomsen, W. Kurth, M. Dougherty, D. Gurnett, and D. Young, Magnetic signatures of plasma-depleted flux tubes in the inner magnetosphere of Saturn, *Geophysical Research Letters*, 34, L14108, doi:10.1029/2007GL030374, 2007

(22) C. S. Arridge, C. Russell, K. Khurana, N. Achilleos, **N. André**, A. Rymer, M. Dougherty, and A. Coates, The mass of Saturn's magnetodisc, *Geophysical Research Letters*, 34, 2007

(21) M. F. Thomsen, J. P. DiLorenzo, D. J. McComas, D. T. Young, F. J. Crary, D. Delapp, D. B. Reisenfeld, and **N. André**, Assessment of the magnetospheric contribution to the suprathermal ions in Saturn's foreshock, *Journal of Geophysical Research*, 112, 2007

(20) Rymer, A. M., B. H. Mauk, T. W. Hill, C. Paranicas, **N. André**, E. C. Sittler, D. G. Mitchell, H. T. Smith, R. E. Johnson, A. J. Coates, D. T. Young, S. J. Bolton, M. F. Thomsen, and M. K. Dougherty, Electron sources in Saturn's magnetosphere, *Journal of Geophysical Research*, 112, A02201, 2007

2006

(19) Clarke, K, **N. André**, D. J. Andrews, A. J. Coates, S. W. H. Cowley, M. K. Dougherty, H. J. McAndrews, J. D. Nichols, T. R. Robinson, and D. M. Wright, Cassini observations of planetary-period oscillations in Saturn's magnetopause, *Geophysical Research Letters*, 33, L23104, 2006

(18) F. M. Neubauer, H. Backes, M. Dougherty, A. Wennmacher, C. Russell, A. Coates, D. Young, N. Achilleos, **N. André**, C. Arridge, C. Bertucci, G. Jones, K. Khurana, T. Knetter, A. Law, G. Lewis, and J. Saur, Titan's magnetospheric interaction observed by the Cassini Magnetometer experiment: Flybys TA, TB, T3, *Journal of Geophysical Research*, 111, A10220, 2006

(17) R. Hartle, E. Sittler, F. Neubauer, R. Johnson, H. Smith, F. Crary, D. McComas, D. Young, A. Coates, D. Simpson, S. Bolton, D. Reisenfeld, K. Szego, J. Berthelier, A. Rymer, J. Vilppola, J. Steinberg, **N. André**, Initial interpretation of Titan plasma interaction as observed by the Cassini Plasma Spectrometer: Comparison with Voyager 1, *Planetary and Space Science*, 54, 2006

(16) E. Sittler, M. Thomsen, D. Chornay, M. Shappirio, D. Simpson, R. Johnson, H. Smith, A. Coates, A. Rymer, F. Crary, D. McComas, D. Young, D. Reisenfeld, M. Dougherty, **N. André**, J. Connerney, and J. Richardson, Initial results on Saturn's inner plasmasphere as observed by Cassini: Comparison with Voyager, *Planetary and Space Science*, 54, 1197-1210, 2006

(15) R. Hartle, E. Sittler, F. Neubauer, R. Johnson, H. Smith, F. Crary, D. McComas, D. Young, A. Coates, D. Simpson, S. Bolton, D. Reisenfeld, K. Szego, J. Berthelier, A. Rymer, J. Vilppola, J.

Steinberg, and **N. André**, Preliminary interprétation of Titan plasma interaction as observed by the the Cassini Plasma Spectrometer: Comparison with Voyager 1, *Geophysical Research Letters*, 33, L08201, 2006

(14) **N. André** and J. Lemaire, Convective instabilities in the plasmasphere, *Journal of Atmospheric and Solar-Terrestrial Physics*, 68, 213-227, 2006

2005

(13) Ferrière, K.M. and **N. André**, Low-frequency waves and instabilities in stratified, gyrotropic plasmas with arbitrary distribution functions, *Journal of Geophysical Research*, 110, A12201, 2005

(12) **N. André**, M. Dougherty, C. Russell, J. Leisner, and K. Khurana, Dynamics of the Saturnian inner magnetosphere: First inferences from the Cassini magnetometers about small-scale plasma transport in the magnetosphere, *Geophysical Research Letters*, 32, L14S06, 2005

(11) T. W. Hill, A. M. Rymer, J. L. Burch, F. J. Crary, D. T. Young, M. F. Thomsen, D. Delapp, **N. André**, A. J. Coates, and G. R. Lewis, Evidence for rotationally-driven plasma transport in Saturn's magnetosphere, *Geophysical Research Letters*, 32, L14S10, 2005

(10) J. L. Burch, J. Goldstein, T. W. Hill, D. T. Young, F. J. Crary, A. J. Coates, **N. André**, W. S. Kurth, and E. C. Sittler, Properties of local plasma injections in Saturn's magnetosphere, *Geophysical Research Letters*, 32, L14S02, 2005

(9) J. S. Leisner, C. T. Russell, K. K. Khurana, M. K. Dougherty, and **N. André**, Warm flux tubes in the E-ring plasma torus: Initial Cassini magnetometer observations, *Geophysical Research Letters*, 32, L14S08, 2005

(8) E. C. Sittler Jr., M. Thomsen, D. Chornay, M. Shappirio, D. Simpson, R. Johnson, H. Smith, A. Coates, A. Rymer, F. Crary, D. McComas, D. Young, D. Reisenfeld, M. Dougherty, **N. André**, J. Connerney, and J. Richardson, Preliminary results on Saturn's inner plasmasphere as observed by Cassini: Comparison with Voyager, *Geophysical Research Letters*, 32, L14S07, 2005

(7) K. Szego, Z. Bebesi, G. Erdos, L. Foldy, F. Crary, D. McComas, D. Young, S. Bolton, A. Coates, A. Rymer, J. Bethelier, R. Hartle, E. Sittler, D. Reisenfeld, R. Johnson, H. Smith, T. Hill, J. Vippola, J. Steinberg, and **N. André**, The global plasma environment of Titan as observed by Cassini Plasma Spectrometer during the first two close encounters with Titan, *Geophysical Research Letters*, 32, L20S05, 2005

(6) H. Backles, F. Neubauer, M. Dougherty, N. Achilleos, **N. André**, C. Bertucci, G. Jones, K. Khurana, C. Russell, and A. Wennmacher, Titan's magnetic field signature during the TA encounter of Cassini, *Science*, 308, 5724, 992, 2005

(5) M. K. Dougherty, N. Achilleos, **N. André**, C. Arridge, A. Balogh, C. Bertucci, M. Burton, S. Cowley, G. Erdos, G. Giampieri, K.-H. Glassmeier, K. Khurana, J. Leisner, F. Neubauer, C. Russell, E. Smith, D. Southwood, B. Tsurutani, Cassini magnetometer observations during Saturn orbit insertion, *Science*, 307, 5713, 1266, 2005

2004

- (4) **N. André** and K. M. Ferrière, Low-frequency waves and instabilities in stratified, gyrotropic, multicomponent plasmas: Theory and application to the plasma transport in the Io torus, *Journal of Geophysical Research*, 109, A12225, 1-21, 2004

2003

- (3) K. M. Ferrière and **N. André**, A mixed magnetohydrodynamic-kinetic theory of low-frequency waves and instabilities in stratified, gyrotropic, two-component plasmas, *Journal of Geophysical Research*, 108, SMP 24, 1-21, 2003

2002

- (2) K. M. Ferrière and **N. André**, A mixed magnetohydrodynamic-kinetic theory of low-frequency waves and instabilities in homogeneous, gyrotropic plasmas, *Journal of Geophysical Research*, 107, SMP 7, 1-17, 2002
- (1) **N. André**, G. Erdos, M. K. Dougherty, Overview of mirror mode fluctuations in the jovian dusk magnetosheath: Cassini magnetometer observations, *Geophysical Research Letters*, 29, 20, 2002

4. Actes de colloque

- (1) C. Jacquy, V. Génot, E. Budnik, R. Hitier, M. Bouchemit, M. Gangloff, A. Fedorov, B. Cecconi, **N. André**, B. Lavraud, C. Harvey, F. Deriot, D. Heulet, E. Pallier, E. Penou, and J.-L. Pinçon, AMDA, Automated Multi-Dataset Analysis : A web-based service provided by the CDDP, *Astrophysics and Space Science Proceedings*, 2009
- (2) **N. André**, et al., HST Auroral Campaign Observations of Jupiter and Saturn enabled by the CDDP/AMDA and IVOA/Aladin tools, *proceedings of PV 2011* (11 pages)
- (3) **N. André**, et al., Connecting the CDDP/AMDA service to planetary plasma data: Venus, Earth, Mars, Saturn (Jupiter and Comets), *proceedings of Sf2a 2009*, published in 2010 (4 pages)
- (4) **N. André**, Fast rotating magnetospheres of giant planets, *congrès de la SFP, Division Plasmas, Orléans*, 2012 (4 pages)
- (5) Lamy, L. et al., Analysis of HST, VLT and Gemini coordinated observations of Uranus late 2017: a multi-spectral search for auroral signatures, *SF2A-2018: Proceedings of the Annual meeting of the French Society of Astronomy and Astrophysics*. Eds.: P. Di Matteo, F. Billebaud, F. Herpin, N. Lagarde, J.-B. Marquette, A. Robin, O. Venot, pp.29-32, 2018
- (6) Chassela, O. et al., Resistance and gain of the microchannel plate (MCP) detector as a function of temperature, *Proceedings of the SPIE, Volume 11180*, id. 1118030 7 pp., 2019
- (7) **André, N.** et al., Detection efficiency of micro channel plates and channel electron multiplier detectors to penetrating radiation in Space, *Proceedings of the SPIE, Volume 11180*, id. 111806O 15 pp., 2019
- (8) Grigoriev, A. et al., Differential gain stability of a microchannel plate detector dedicated to a neutral particle instrument (JENI) of the JUICE space mission, *Proceedings of the SPIE, Volume 11180*, id. 111806I 10 pp., 2019
- (9) Fedorov, A. et al., Lifetime of channel electron multiplier detectors dedicated to plasma instruments for Solar Orbiter and JUICE space missions, *Proceedings of the SPIE, Volume 11180*, id. 111806F 7 pp., 2019

